

Application of the think-aloud protocols in translation studies: Experience, problems and prospects

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This paper has reviewed 27 Chinese and English papers of translation studies from CNKI and Web of Science, where the Think-aloud Protocols (TAPs) were used to help investigate translation processes. Research goals, participants, texts, and research methods are considered to examine the scope, preciseness, and other aspects of those experiments to reveal the experience, problems, and prospects of using TAPs to guide translation research. This review has found that domestic research pays more attention to translation strategies used while translating, while overseas researchers, in addition to the same topic, also value the data on cognition aspects such as cognitive load, and they also considered post-editing and translation tools, thus demonstrating more diversity. Nevertheless, cognition aspects, such as long/short-term memory and working memory, are somehow overlooked. Numbers of participants also vary, and it's advisable for domestic researchers to gather more data from professional translators and translation learners. The themes of test material vary, also, but both domestic and overseas studies ignored the significance of text types and difficulty on the performance of participants. Multiple research tools have been used for generating more data, such as interviews, questionnaires, and keystroke logging, but in the future, translation quality evaluation tools should also be included to guarantee the quality of designs.

Keywords: think-aloud protocol; translation studies; process analysis, research review

Translation process has always been a key focus for translation studies. Translation is not merely a simple language conversion but a complex cognitive activity that requires translators to creatively express the source text through their understanding, analysis, and reconstruction. In recent years, with the development of cognitive science, more researchers have begun to use tools from cognitive psychology to explore the translation process in depth. Among these tools, the Think-Aloud Protocols (TAPs), a qualitative research method, has been widely applied in translation studies due to its ability to record and analyse translators' real-time cognitive activities during the translation process. This method provides insight into how translators manage cognitive load, resolve ambiguities, and navigate shifts between source and target languages in real time. As translation involves both conscious problem-solving and subconscious automatised processes, TAPs allow researchers to distinguish between deliberate decision-making and intuitive translation strategies. Additionally, TAPs can be combined with eye-tracking and keystroke logging to form a more comprehensive picture of the cognitive mechanisms at play in translation.

Dörnyei (2007) classifies the TAPs as a type of reflective method within qualitative research tools, describing its process as “verbalizing inner speech without providing any analysis or explanation”. In translation studies, this method can be used to gather empirical data on the translation process (Jääskeläinen, 2010). Researchers can use verbal reports to uncover the cognitive processes involved in translation, exploring factors such as translation strategies, translation steps, translation units, attention allocation, and emotional attitudes (Fraser, 1996). As a primary research method in cognitive psychology, the application of the TAPs first appeared in the 1980s (Gesloff, 1986). Interest in the method later declined, but since the late 20th century, scholars both domestically and internationally have re-applied this method to study the translation process. The application of the Think-Aloud Protocol can help researchers obtain data on translators' thinking processes during translating, providing strong support for revealing translation strategies, translation steps, attention allocation, etc. However, this method also faces a few controversies and challenges. Researchers question whether TAPs can provide effective verbal data due to participants' insufficient language expression abilities or whether the requirement for participants to “think aloud” while translating might lead to insufficient translation results. Nonetheless, a review of dozens of TAPs experiments in translation has shown that these issues do not necessarily arise. Instead, problems such as a lack of rigorous experimental design, shallow experimental objectives, and low effectiveness of experimental results have prevented it from being fully utilised in translation research. Therefore, how to effectively use the tool in translation studies and expand its boundaries is an urgent issue in relevant research.

This paper aims to summarise and assess present domestic and foreign TAPs experiments, and through analysing their research design in terms of research objectives, participant numbers, text selection, research process, etc., valuable experience could be gained for further reference. The 27 papers reviewed are from China National Knowledge Infrastructure (CNKI) and Web of Science from 2000 to 2023, and attempts are made to provide reliable suggestions and improvement ideas for future research on applying the Think-Aloud Protocol to translation studies.

Research goals: Diversified but unsystematic

According to the country differences, the research objectives of translation TAPs in China and abroad are shown in the following diagram:

Figure 1
 Research goals of China domestic TAPs in translation studies

Based on the review and summary of the research objectives of nine empirical studies on the TAPs in translation from the CNKI, it is found that domestic research in this field focuses on two main aspects: translator’s strategies and translation units. Five experiments focus on strategy research, where four of them aim to observe students’ translation strategies and displays different features in goal setting. For instance, Liu (2012) and Qin (2018) aim to guide translation teaching by evaluating the effectiveness of students’ application of translation strategies. Qiu (2023) mainly observe the impact of psychological anxiety on students’ translation strategies. Cabré (2012) primarily focus on describing the characteristics of students’ use of translation strategies during English to Chinese translation. Experiments solely focusing on translation units (Liu, 2012; Yang et al., 2015; Yang & Wang, 2019;) compared the size of translation units between student translators and professional translators to guide students in adjusting future translation behaviour. Other studies, such as Geng et al. (2018), use the TAPs to test participants’ attention to translation problems and observe the improvement in the retranslation of the source text after one round of learning. Xu (2020) experimented with significantly different participants and objectives compared to other studies. They observe the entire thinking process of translation scorers assessing CET 4 translation results, which expands the realm of application compared to previous experiments.

In contrast, overseas TAPs have experienced wider use, and their research goals are summarised in the following graph.

Figure 2
 Research goals of overseas TAPs in translation studies

The diagram above illustrates two main categories of TAPs, with one branch closely connected to cognitive psychology and the other to translation ability and skills. Specifically, the cognitive

psychology branch research offers abundant information regarding cognitive effort (Latorraca, 2018; Vieira, 2017), problem-solving (Minchenkov, 2019), cognitive processing and conceptualisation (Olohan, 2002), translation creativity (Cho, 2006), meta language awareness and ability (Woll, 2018), post-editing as a means for translation analytical ability activation (Chernovaty & Kovalchuk, 2021). The translation ability and skills branch feature four pieces of research: the improvement of pragmatic awareness and its effect on translation results (Akbari et al., 2021), the significance of TAPs for advanced translation in improving translation results (Dorer, 2023), translation strategy analysis (Atari, 2005), and the application of TAPs for improving cultural transmission (Daniel et al., 2011).

In terms of experience, translation strategy research constitutes a major part of TAP studies in translation. Future research can continue to delve deeper into this area. Additionally, TAP research should stay aligned with the theoretical and practical trends in translation studies to broaden its scope, such as post-editing studies, translation outcome improvement research, and pragmatic studies conducted abroad. Furthermore, with the continuous development of machine translation and artificial intelligence translation, TAP should actively explore the field of machine-assisted translation to gain deep insights into how translators utilise various auxiliary resources and to address the challenges posed by technological advancements in the translation field.

Valuable lessons could be learned from the objectives, and also, several issues should be noticed. First of all, there is a pressing need to enhance the precision, focus, and depth of conceptual frameworks, especially in the realm of translation strategy research. This area requires urgent refinement due to two primary issues: on one hand, the concept of translation strategies is often unclear. Previous studies have not clearly defined “translation strategy” before aiming to observe it. Volkova (2014) defines translation strategy as encompassing the thoughts, approaches, methods, and procedures involved in the translation process. Thoughts are aligned with certain macro theories or derived from translation experience, approaches are feasible ways to achieve goals, methods are specific means to reach goals, and procedures are the sequence of steps to achieve goals. Therefore, a translation strategy is a combination of theoretical strategy and practical means. For example, consulting a dictionary to obtain word meanings during translation has been defined as a translation strategy (Cabre, 2012)). However, upon closer inspection, “consulting a dictionary” should be considered a means or approach rather than a strategy. Generally, “strategy” should be understood as an overall thought, layout, and plan, belonging to the macro-level “theoretical guidance,” such as “domestication,” “foreignisation,” or “functional equivalence”. Observing only the means of translation can lead researchers to remain superficial, unable to deeply consider the translator’s overall thinking about the text. Given the limited number of translation means and approaches, focusing solely on this aspect can result in a lack of innovation in research. Conversely, the general examination of “translation strategies” frequently leads to a deficiency in thorough investigation among academics. Various categories of writing provide unique translation difficulties, and even within the same genre, writers’ writing styles might diverge considerably. Therefore, the use of TAP to randomly chosen texts does not derive any advantage from textual universality. To improve the significance, accuracy, and efficiency of their research, researchers should integrate significant investigative components, such as specialised vocabulary, sentences, rhetorical techniques, context, and themes.

Secondly, the conversion rate and recurrence rate of results from think-aloud protocol studies are relatively low. The review reveals that domestic studies only address problem identification, not problem-solving, and there is little effort to translate findings into practical solutions. Additionally, a common issue faced by both domestic and international research is the absence of follow-up think-aloud experiments conducted by the same group of researchers. “One-time” experiments fail to maximise the comparative potential of think-aloud studies. As mentioned earlier, think-aloud

experiments aimed at guiding translation instruction only summarize the cognitive and behavioral characteristics of the translation process, pointing out deficiencies. However, after proposing theoretical guidance, corresponding methods are not applied to translation instruction to observe their subsequent effects.

Furthermore, as a conventional research tool in cognitive psychology, the think-aloud protocol has not fully realized its potential in translation research. Current studies primarily focus on describing the cognitive processes of translation; there is a dearth of comprehensive inquiries into the underlying cognitive components. For instance, what cognitive factors lead to failures in the translation process? What is the correlation between translation decisions and the long-term memory, short-term memory, working memory, and language cognition mechanisms of translators? Researchers in this subject should conduct more comprehensive investigations into the research methodologies of cognitive psychology and actively investigate the psychological mechanisms that are involved in the translation process.

Participants: Not as rigid as expected

The number of participants and backgrounds of domestic and overseas TAPs experiments are as follows:

Figure 3
 Numbers of participants in China and overseas TAPs experiments

Figure 4
 Participant background of TAPs in China

Figure 5

Participant background of overseas TAPs

The numbers of participants in TAPs experiments at home and abroad are slightly different, which is mainly caused by the difference in the extreme values of the experiments. Respectively, 9 Chinese experiments and 18 overseas experiments are included in this research. The number of participants in China’s experiments ranges from 4 to 30, with an average of 15.67; for overseas experiments, the number ranges from 2 to 66, with an average of 18.44. In domestic TAPs experiments, there are 2 studies with fewer than 10 participants, 5 studies with 11-20 participants, and 2 studies with more than 20 participants. In overseas TAPs, there are 7 studies with fewer than 10 participants, 5 studies with 11-20 participants, and 6 studies with more than 20 participants. Although the maximum number of participants in overseas TAPs experiments is 2.2 times that of domestic experiments, the average numbers are not significantly different. Comparison reveals that domestic TAPs experiments with fewer than 20 participants have slightly more participants than overseas ones. Regardless of whether they are conducted domestically or internationally, the majority of tests typically involve 11–20 participants domestically, while 10 almost marks a half split of overseas tests. This could be attributed to researchers considering the data analysis workload, which has been confirmed in previous tests. Jääskeläinen (2002) summarised 108 think-aloud protocols and translation research papers published between 1980 and 2000, showing that sample sizes ranged from 4 to 24 participants, with most studies having around 10 participants. Upon observing the foreign experiment with the highest number of participants (66), it is noted that the data is not durable in the long term, since the texts used in this test were vocabulary items rather than paragraphs, resulting in a smaller amount of verbal report data and less cognitive load. With the exception of the extreme data, the general patterns in the number of participants in think-aloud experiments are consistent both locally and abroad.

Secondly, there is a significant difference in the backgrounds of participants in domestic and overseas TAPs. Within the home setting, a significant majority of 76% of participants are students majoring in English, suggesting a substantial dependence on this particular group for research purposes. Additional participant categories consist of non-professional translators, comprising 7% of the total, new translation learners, accounting for 9%, professional translators, making up 4%, and translation raters, also comprising 4%. This demonstrates a strong emphasis on English major students, with limited inclusion of individuals from professional and non-professional translation backgrounds. Studies conducted abroad indicate a greater variety of participants’ backgrounds. Translation students form the largest group at 36%, followed by professional participants at 30%, non-professional participants at 23%, English major students at 7%, and non-professional translators at

6%. This distribution demonstrates a wider incorporation of diverse backgrounds, highlighting a more holistic approach to selecting participants of overseas researchers.

The main distinction between domestic and foreign TAP studies resides in the diversity of participant backgrounds. The participation in domestic studies is predominantly composed of English major students, accounting for 75% of the participants, while other groups are considerably underrepresented. Overseas studies, in comparison, exhibit a more equitable allocation, encompassing a substantial number of both professional translators and non-professional participants. This indicates a more comprehensive and diverse approach. The diversity in participant selection can potentially impact the extent and relevance of the research findings, as studies conducted overseas may provide insights from a broader spectrum of translation experiences and skills.

Unlike quantitative research, where larger sample sizes are preferred, qualitative research primarily generates textual data. Excessively large sample sizes can lead to prolonged analysis, heavy workload, and the inclusion of redundant data, ultimately reducing research efficiency. Dörnyei (2005) suggests that the sample size in qualitative research should be flexible and adjusted according to the research process. He recommends an initial sample size of 6-10 participants for qualitative studies generating textual data, which can be increased to 30 participants if resources and computer-assisted analysis are available. Glaser et al. (1968) propose that the optimal total sample size should be determined when additional samples yield only repetitive views of existing opinions, indicating that the sample size is sufficient for the research.

In practice, researchers often consider existing reliable theoretical results along with practical constraints such as time and funding. Different sampling methods should be employed based on research objectives. For instance, a think-aloud protocol aimed at guiding translation instruction can use stratified sampling, as suggested by Patton (2002), to achieve sample differentiation and ensure overall representativeness of the experimental results. Stratified sampling can also broaden the scope of research findings. To effectively guide translation instruction, researchers need to understand the behavioral characteristics of students at various proficiency levels rather than focusing on a single level. For think-aloud protocols involving professional translators, random sampling based on the type of experimental text and the translators' backgrounds can be used to collect as much non-redundant data as possible until saturation is reached.

Additionally, participant selection should be more rigorous. Many studies involve professional translators of varying levels, but the criteria for judging a professional translator can vary. It can be based on years of experience or word count. If word count is the criterion, the threshold should be set and reliably measured. The translators' familiarity with the experimental texts should also be considered. In an experiment featuring Traditional Chinese Medicine texts some participants are from foreign language schools (Pritzker, 2014; Relojo et al., 2016). Based on their think-aloud data, these students generally lack a background in Traditional Chinese Medicine. Expressions such as “不荣则痛” (pain is the result of inner weakness) and the “症” (symptom) in “痛经症” (dysmenorrhea) in the source text are beyond the comprehension of ordinary students. In such cases, observations of participants' translation strategies should consider how students reason and make translation decisions, beyond just their translation techniques.

Texts used in TAPs : The element that calls for more attention

Not all current TAPs offer the data on the length and type of texts used in their TAPs, and reference data is summarised in the following table.

Table 1

Comparison of text types and word counts in domestic and overseas translation studies

No.	Domestic text type	Word count	No.	Overseas text type	Word count
1	CET-4 Test Paper	140–160	1	News - Nature	157
2	Prose	176	2	Popular Science	178
3	Prose	196	3	Political Speech	222
4	Traditional Chinese Medicine Text	238	4	Western Medicine and Political news	844
5	Novel	112	5	Famous Quotes (in German)	42
6	Popular Science Material	187	6	Questionnaire Survey	22 items
7	Popular Science	178	7	Science - Physics	2000
8	Speech	191	8	Medicine - Cancer	20 minutes
			9	Law	103
			10	News (in Dutch)	500
			11	Novel	140
			12	Children's literature	56
			13	Instruction of online game	109

Note: All information are arranged merely according the word count of the material used, and some papers have used more than 1 piece of text, such as item 11-13 of overseas research are from the same paper.

Upon analysing the word count and textual genres utilised in both domestic and foreign TAPs studies in translation, no researchers have thoroughly taken into account the text types, length, and difficulty in their experimental design. The given data shows that domestic experiment texts primarily comprise paragraphs, whereas overseas experiments encompass paragraphs, vocabulary, brief phrases, questions, and booklets. Out of the experiments included in the statistics, 3 domestic experiments did not provide information about the text type, making up 33.3% of the domestic experiments (Geng et al., 2018; Liu, 2012; Qin, 2018). Among the foreign experiments analyzed, there are four that did not mention the word count of the texts (Cho, 2006; Daniel et al., 2011; Olohan, 2002), excluding projects that involve questionnaires, leaflets, and post-editing tasks which cannot be solely measured by word count (Chernovaty & Kovalchuk, 2021; Dorer, 2023; Vieira, 2017). This proportion is significantly lower than that observed in domestic experiments. Regarding text kinds, the texts utilised in domestic experiments can be broadly categorised into three groups: literary texts (consisting of 3 items), practical texts (including traditional Chinese medicine and popular science, with 3 pieces), and other sorts of texts (such as CET-4 and speeches). Conversely, out of all foreign experiments, only 2 incorporated literary text (Atari, 2005; Cifuentes-Férez & Rojo, 2015), while the majority of the rest employed practical texts. Hence, there exists a substantial disparity in text genre preferences between domestic and international research. Typically, texts ranging from 150 to 200 words are commonly used in both domestic and overseas experiments.

Among all the observed studies, only the experiment by Zheng (2014) offered information on text difficulty. This study not only explains the general principles for selecting experimental texts but also proposes three specific rules regarding text theme, text quality, and text complexity. Analyzing the difficulty of experimental texts is necessary. If the text is too simple, it may not fully reflect the participants' translation abilities and their real level in solving translation problems, resulting in suboptimal experimental outcomes. Conversely, if the experimental text exceeds the participants' capabilities, causing excessive cognitive load, it will affect participants' performance and may result in researchers obtaining disordered and unstructured verbal data. Therefore, analyzing text difficulty is essential. Text difficulty can be measured by considering three aspects: the source text, the translation task, and the translator's ability. Campbell (1999) suggests that the difficulty of texts in

translation can be evaluated based on the text type, which affects text difficulty, as agreed by House and Hatim. He advocates assessing text difficulty by considering the burden on working memory, especially texts involving long-term memory, those that cannot be quickly reacted to in a short time, and those containing complex grammatical structures. Research shows that vocabulary types, such as verbs, abstract meanings, and complex noun phrases, affect text difficulty. Text type and linguistic issues, such as vocabulary and syntax, are the main factors influencing text difficulty (Campbell, 1999). Reiss (1981) proposed five factors that affect text difficulty: subject content, register, language type, text pragmatics, and historical and cultural background. Nord (1991) categorised problems that cause translation difficulty into text type problems, pragmatic problems, cultural problems, and language pair problems, which refer to differences between the source language and the target language (Nord, 1991). The issues mentioned by these scholars align with elements of cognitive abilities and the mobilisation of long-term and short-term memory in cognitive science.

In the 21st century, many researchers use eye-tracking and keystroke logging methods to provide reliable evidence for assessing text difficulty. For instance, Liu et al. (2019) conduct empirical research using these methods and propose that quantitative indicators based on text characteristics (readability, word frequency, and non-literary nature) indeed influence the difficulty of the source text, while subjective judgement remains a cost-effective method for determining text difficulty. However, this experiment does not include text rhetoric in the scope of text difficulty, as the use of rhetoric does not necessarily directly correlate with word difficulty. Sun (2011) uses the NASA-TLX task load index model in an empirical study to show that text readability affects text difficulty to a certain extent, and pre-translation of texts can help assess text difficulty. Additionally, Sun suggests that translators with different levels of translation ability have different capacities for identifying translation problems, resulting in varying cognitive loads and translation times. Therefore, translation time alone cannot be used to measure difficulty.

Based on the ideas of various researchers, text difficulty analysis can be considered from the following aspects: (1) linguistic issues: vocabulary and syntax; (2) textual issues: theme, rhetoric, and context; (3) language pair issues: language differences; (4) cultural layer differences; (5) relationship between experiment participants and texts: whether participants have previously encountered the text type and their translation abilities.

These five aspects can be categorised as text-level difficulty considerations. In practical application, analysts can also integrate various cognitive psychology parameters, such as perception, memory, and cognitive load, and comprehensively consider these factors. Before employing the Think-Aloud Protocol, it is essential to thoroughly prepare the experimental texts and use both quantitative and qualitative analysis tools to assist in measuring the text's difficulty.

Researchers can analyse text difficulty themselves or use text analysis tools to examine the linguistic aspects of the texts. For example, by using the "Text Analyzer" feature provided by the AI analysis tool Cathovon Language Hub, one can review the level of vocabulary and syntactic complexity of an input English text according to the CEFR (Common European Framework of Reference) and Cambridge Scale standards. This tool also indicates the general English proficiency level required to engage with such texts. As a tool developed by native English speakers, it mainly provides insights into the "reading difficulty" of a text. However, there are distinctions between reading difficulty and translation difficulty, since translation would involve more cultural and contextual considerations. To accurately gauge the true complexity of a text in the context of translation, researchers can employ pre-translation and use questionnaires or interviews to collect opinions and evaluations, thereby ensuring the validity of the experiment.

IMPLICATIONS

In domestic research, only the work of Zheng (2014) employed a five-point scale and invited two experts to assess the results of translation in experiments. It is beyond question that for every experimental element, scientific scrutiny is vital in ensuring its reliability or validity. Equally important, the quality assessment of a text provides a direct indication of how well participants' translation strategies work. Can process analysis discover the real problems during the translation process without considering results? The necessity of evaluating translation quality in experiments should depend on what the experiment aims to achieve. When the ultimate objective is translation teaching and the reason behind conducting an experiment is student translators' strategies during translation, evaluating translational outcomes becomes highly imperative before data analysis. Otherwise, the analysis of the Think-Aloud data will merely describe the cognitive process without correlating the translation process with the translation results, failing to identify potential cognitive issues in the translation process and to provide final guidance.

In terms of research methods, besides using TAPs as the primary research tool, researchers also employ other methods as supplements to obtain better data results. In domestic experiments, questionnaires are commonly used by researchers after think-aloud sessions to understand participants' self-assessment of their "think-aloud" (Cabré, 2012; Qin, 2018; Qiu, 2023; Zheng, 2014). In contrast, overseas research employs a more diverse range of experimental tools, including retrospective interviews (Akbari et al., 2021; Dorer, 2023), eye-tracking (Vieira, 2017), and Translog (Hjort-Pedersen & Faber, 2010; Latorraca, 2018). The diversification of research methods is worth taking advantage of, but the methods of research, especially the more popular questionnaire methods and retrospect interviews should be oriented to guide experiments to obtain richer data.

CONCLUSION

After examining current Think-Aloud Protocol (TAP) studies on translation conducted in China and other countries, the following recommendations can be proposed for further research.

Firstly, a more varied approach should be employed in conducting investigations. The current research approach exhibits a degree of consistency and is in immediate need of broadening its cognitive horizons. This entails actively incorporating quantitative research methods and improving the utilisation and recognition of measurable variables to enhance the scope and comprehensiveness of research. The integration of qualitative TAP research methods and quantitative research is an enduring trend, thus prompting the need for further investigation in areas such as text complexity, quantitative assessment of translation outcomes, and multiple regression analysis of various factors influencing translation results. Furthermore, the process of designing experiments can be enhanced by incorporating more advanced and systematic approaches. This involves not only conducting isolated TAP experiments, but also designing comprehensive experiments that are guided by specific objectives. For example, one objective could be to observe the effects of a particular translation teaching method or stimulus on the translation process and outcomes.

Furthermore, it is necessary to further explore deeper into the theoretical aims. Previous study endeavours have sought to illustrate a deficiency in theoretical profundity and a limited concentration on research themes. It is essential to carefully analyse the conceptual implications of the TAP in translation and ensure that research goals are closely aligned with current trends and practical requirements. This will guarantee that the research accurately represents the attributes and orientations of current investigations. At present, domestic TAP investigations mostly focus on surface-level translation processes, specifically "translation units" and "translation strategies". The

research findings in this field exhibit a degree of “predictability”, which reduces the practical significance of the study aims. Xu (2020) argue that translators should have the ability to understand the implied meanings of a specific morpheme in different terminology related to Traditional Chinese Medicine. Nevertheless, they fail to offer any recommendations for cultivating this perceptive skill, leading to the research findings being solely descriptive. Translation researchers might expand the application of the TAP as a technique for psychological study by using interdisciplinary theoretical knowledge from cognitive psychology. Additionally, they can explore the relationship between translation and cognitive psychological aspects such as memory, reasoning, and strategy. This technique improves the applicability of study findings to the intricate cognitive structure of sophisticated prediction models in the age of artificial intelligence.

Furthermore, it is necessary to provide more precise details regarding the study materials. The resources used in modern research show a wide range and lack specificity. To enhance the usefulness and efficiency of research findings in the field of translation, it is crucial to focus the study on particular texts and situations. When conducting TAP experiments in translation, the main consideration for selecting texts is their level of “difficulty”. Additionally, the choice of topics also considers the difficulty level of the text but does not take into account the specific type of text. Consequently, there is a lack of recognition of probes in experiments and a failure to provide universally meaningful information for the analysis of different types of text genres. As a result, researchers can categorise texts based on their characteristics and research the translation process of different text categories. Furthermore, it would be prudent to analyse the challenges that translators face when confronted with polysemy, rhetorical techniques, and other intricacies in the process of translation.

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